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URL: <https://cve.report/CVE-2022-24584>
URL: <https://cve.report/CVE-2022-24584/mitre>
URL: <https://cve.report/CVE-2022-24584/nist>
URL: https://cve.report/CVE-2022-24584/cve_org
URL: <https://cve.report/CVE-2022-24584.pdf>
URL: <https://cve.mitre.org/cgi-bin/cvename.cgi?name=CVE-2022-24584>
URL: <https://nvd.nist.gov/vuln/detail/CVE-2022-24584>
URL: <https://www.cve.org/CVERecord?id=CVE-2022-24584>
URL: <https://demo.yubico.com/otp/verify>
URL: <https://pastebin.com/7iLR1EbW>
URL: <https://upload.yubico.com/>
URL: <https://pastebin.com/xAh8uV6J>
URL: <https://twitter.com/i/web/status/1524450936709603332>
URL: <https://www.reddit.com/r/netcve/comments/ungpqc/cve202224584/>

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<https://pastebin.com/7iLR1EbW>

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CVE-2022-24584: Incorrect access control in Yubico OTP functionality of the Yu bi Key hardware tokens along with the Yubico OTP validation server

<https://boards.4channel.org/g/thread/86801252>
<https://i.4cdn.org/g/1651680877341.jpg>
https://anonfiles.com/Tav0bddby7/CVE-2022-24584_pdf
<https://cdn-130.anonfiles.com/Tav0bddby7/3602e604-1651679466/CVE-2022-24584.pdf>
https://anonfiles.com/Ddk0d4d7y7/yubico_zip
<https://cdn-104.anonfiles.com/Ddk0d4d7y7/9f80ed64-1651685867/yubico.zip>

All links are included in the Internet Archive/Wayback Machine
Screenshots for Proof of Vulnerability are included as attachments in the PDF.

Hello,

I am writing to you to report a security vulnerability in the Yubico OTP Validation Server. I assess the severity NOT to be High, mostly because Yubico OTP isn't as widely used as the alternatives, such as U2f, FIDO etc., but regardless I believe it must be published and an advisory issued.

The product claims made on the product page state that the Yubico OTPs are hardware bound and unclonable. This might be correct AFTER the configuration has been written to the device. But, someone could make a duplicate device using the same configuration. After reprogramming, the new configuration will have to be uploaded to the Yubico servers. I have shown that the server will accept any uploaded configuration and, even though the upload form asks for the serial number, it is not utilized to make sure that the configuration is actually bound to a particular device.

The conclusion is that only OTPs starting with "cc" are hardware bound, since they are programmed at the factory. In the case where the customer wants to program custom secrets, the new configuration uploaded to the Yubico server (OTPs starting with "vv") are not hardware bound and the serial number isn't checked.

I have already applied for a CVE ID (CVE-2022-24584) but haven't otherwise publicized these findings and I leave it to you.

Thank you,
[REDACTED]
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<https://pastebin.com/xAh8uV6J>

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Response to the disputing comments from the Vendor:

Nowhere is claimed that the secrets can be extracted from the device. The vulnerability lies in the fact that the Yubico OTP Validation Server (Yubico Validation Service, YubiCloud) ASKS for the SERIAL NUMBER of the device when uploading a new configuration, but does not, in fact, check that a particular generated OTP was actually generated by the device with that serial number. Basically, the "Serial Number" field during the upload of a new configuration is not validated in any way and does not take part in any verification. The server does not differentiate between same secrets stored on different devices, or same device Serial Number having many configurations (even if those configurations were uploaded by someone using a random made-up serial number).

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